

Some Biologically Interesting Natural Products with Novel Structural Features

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The chemistry and prospects of some biologically interesting natural products with novel structural features isolated in recent years from plants used in traditional medicine are discussed. The mechanism of transformation of the aglycones of saponins from *Terminalia bellerica* and *Medicago hispida* is also covered.

Natural Products Chemistry has contributed significantly towards the development of modern medicines. Many of the modern medicines are modifications or survivals of ancient herbalism. The structure elucidation of natural products which was once an attractive area of research is no longer the spearhead of the subject. The application of the powerful spectroscopic techniques has tremendously eased the problem. However, although the routine adoption of these techniques in structure elucidation studies may appear to have created a limitation on the generation of new chemical knowledge, these methodologies have nevertheless opened up new vistas, and research activities are now moving forward into areas which were otherwise inaccessible. While much of our basic chemical knowledge was previously derived from degradative studies, its extension today rests primarily on the synthesis of natural products and their analogs and their modifications for a variety of purposes. The real spearhead of natural products chemistry now lies in studies associated with biological investigations leading to the understanding of structure-activity relationship. The structural study, however, has not lost its importance from a practical standpoint. We have seen in recent years the beneficial effects and industrial stimulus provided by such natural products as taxol, a diterpene (anticancer)¹, artemisinin, a sesquiterpene lactone (antimalarial)², azadirachtin, a tetranortriterpenoid (antifeedant)^{3,4} and forskolin, a diterpene (hypotensive, cardioactive)^{5,8}. Bioactive natural products often have highly complex structures with many chiral centres, which may determine biological activity. Such complex compounds cannot be synthesized economically with the present state of chemical knowledge and development of process for large-scale isolation from potential natural sources or their partial synthesis from widely available natural products becomes imperative. This article presents a survey of some potentially important natural products with complex structural features.

Cleomeolide

The macrocyclic diterpene lactone, cleomeolide (1) was first isolated by us^{9,10} in the late 1970s and its complete structure and stereochemistry were determined by means

of nmr, X-ray and CD methods. Burke *et al.*¹¹ isolated and characterized it subsequently and described some interesting reactions encountered during the structural investigation. The host plant is *Cleome icosandro* (Syn. *Cleome viscosa*) which is a sticky herb widely distributed in India. It has yellow flowers and strong penetrating odour. The leaves are rubefacient, vesicant, sudorifice and also used in external applications for wounds and ulcers. The plant is used by the poorer people as vegetable after discarding the flowers and pods¹².

The unprecedented structural features of cleomeolide encompass a 12-membered carbocyclic ring *cis*-fused to a methylene cyclohexane ring as well as a 7-membered α,β -

unsaturated lactone whose double bond is at the bridge-head position. The unique carbocyclic framework arises by a nine-membered carbon chain *cis*-fused in 2,6-fashion to a methylenecyclohexane core.

The novelty of the carbon skeleton (2) named cleomane¹⁰ present in cleomeolide was revealed by its ¹³C nmr spectral data which demonstrated the occurrence of only one *sp*³ quaternary carbon atom, a structural feature unprecedented in naturally occurring diterpenes. A somewhat similar carbocyclic framework containing diterpene verticillol (3) was isolated by Karlsson *et al.*¹³ from *Sciadopitys verticillata* more or less during the same period of time.

The biogenetic pathway of formation of cleomeolide may be envisaged to arise either by the oxidative cyclization of geranyl linalool epoxide¹⁰ (Scheme 1) or via head-to-tail cyclization of geranyl geranyl pyrophosphate¹¹ (Scheme 2.) However, one would be tempted to prefer the former considering the oxygenation pattern in the molecule.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

The macrocyclic diterpenes cembrene¹⁴ and casbene¹⁵ are regarded as the prototypes of a variety of natural products showing significant biological activity¹⁶. Phorbol esters are known cocarcinogens¹⁷, and jatrophone¹⁸, gnidi-macrin¹⁹, and asperdiol²⁰ are reported for their antileukemic activity whereas taxol¹ is drawing much attention in recent years for its development as a drug mainly for breast and ovarian cancer²¹. Besides cleomeolide itself having a great potential for its biological activity its chemical convertibility to a tricycyclic system analogous to that found in taxane has created much interest. Cleomeolide in benzene or acetone on oxidation with Jones reagent at room temperature furnished the ketone¹⁰ 4 which on treatment with 10% KOH and MeOH at room temperature afforded two products¹¹ 5 and 6. The interesting isomeric lactone 6 which was characterized by X-ray crystallography¹¹ has structural relationship to the taxane diterpenes such as taxol 7.

It is noteworthy that taxol is isolated from *Taxus yews* which are rare plant species requiring special agroclimatic conditions to grow. Moreover, these yews take longer period to get matured. The increasing demand for taxol has prompted the investigators to search for alternative source for this diterpene or its potential analogs. *Cleome icosandra* which is widely distributed in India and probably in other tropical countries, may be a potential source for cleomeolide which may be required as a precursor to analogs of taxol.

The first total synthesis of (+)-cleomeolide has been accomplished in enantioselective fashion from optically pure Wieland-Miescher ketone 8 by Paquette *et al.*^{22,23}. Their well-designed and ultimately successful stratagem was dependent on effective use of a diagnosable interdependence of functional group development and adoption of serviceable global energy conformational minima. The successful use of these tactics will encourage the adoption of related possibilities for stereocontrolled macrocyclic ring assembly in future synthetic ventures.

The key steps in the synthesis were (a) improved conversion of optically pure Wieland-Miescher ketone 8 into dienol ether 9 and oxidative cleavage of the latter to aldehyde 10, (b) avoidance of complications arising from steric blockade of C-15 for introduction of the methylene group at that site, (c) employment of an intramolecular Wadsworth-Emmons cyclization for macrocyclic ring

construction, (d) modulation of the conformation adopted by the medium ring by diastereofacial control of epoxidation of the C-3/C-4 double bond and (e) intramolecular cyclization of the epoxy acid derived from **10** by nucleophilic capture at the more substituted oxiranyl carbon. The deep-seated topographical change that occurs during the formation of **11** projects the macrocyclic ring quasi-axially from the methylenecyclohexane subunit. Thus the intramolecular cyclization to set the bridgehead double bond was facilitated. Compound **10** on treatment with the combination of iodine and Ag_2O in aqueous dioxane provided the desired product **11** in modest yield.

Verticillol

The macrocyclic diterpene alcohol verticillol **3** was isolated from the wood of *Sciadopitys verticillata* Sieb. et Zucc. (Taxodiaceae)¹³. The structure of verticillol **3** was elucidated from NMR-LIS studies on it as well as its correlation to the diepoxide **12** whose structure was established by direct single crystal X-ray analysis. The absolute configuration of **3** was determined by CD data of the verticillol norketodiepoxide **13**. The carbocyclic framework of verticillol **3** is somewhat akin to that of cleomeolide **1**. However, the presence of the substituents (3-OH and C-8 \rightarrow C-4 lactone) in appropriate positions in **1** facilitates its conversion to compounds analogous to taxane diterpenes.

Mimusopic acid and mimusopsic acid

Triterpenoids have attracted considerable interest in recent years because of the widespread reports on their useful biological activities^{24,25} and practical applications²⁶⁻²⁸. *Mimusops elengi* is a widely distributed tree in India and is held in high repute in Indian traditional medicine. Bassic acid **15** which is considered to be a chemical marker for the presence of saponins of protobassic acid **14**, was isolated previously from the plant^{29,30}. Two new pentacyclic triterpene acids, mimusopic acid **16** and mimusopsic acid **17** possessing the novel migrated oleanane skeleton, mimusopane **19** have recently been isolated from that acid hydrolysate of the MeOH extract of the seeds of the plant³¹. Their structures were elucidated by spectroscopic methods and chemical transformations. The co-occurrence of acids **15**, **16**, and **17** strongly indicated that both acids **16** and **17** could be artefacts formed from bassic acid **15** during acid hydrolysis of the saponin fraction. In fact, when a solution of bassic acid **15** in MeOH-HCl (aq.) was boiled under reflux for 4 h and worked up as usual for the isolation of the products, acids **16** (40%), **17** (10%), and unconverted acid **15** (50%) were obtained. Although transformation of protobassic acid **14** to bassic acid **15** is

Scheme 3

known to occur by facile dehydration of 6 β (axial)-hydroxyl group under acidic condition which is under strong steric 1,3-diaxial interactions with 4 β -, 8 β - and 10 β -axial methyls, further conversions of acid **15** to acids **16** and **17** are unprecedented. The mechanism of formation of acids **16** and **17** is rationalized as shown in Scheme 3. It is apparent from Dreiding model inspection that 1,3-diaxial interaction exists in acid **15** involving 10 β -, 4 β -methyls, and 2 β -hydroxyl group. Protonation of the 5,6-double bond followed by migration of the 10 β -methyl to 5 β -position, resulting in reversal of conformation of the A-ring substituents, release the strains and lead to the formation of mimusopic acid **16** with the novel 5,10-friedooleanane skeleton. It is conceivable that the diallylic nature of 11-CH₂ of acid **16** is prone to aerial oxidation leading to the intermediate formation of 11-hydroxy compound **18**. Elimination of the 11-hydroxy of acid **18**, migration of the 9:10 double bond to 9:11 position, and formation of 23 \rightarrow 10 oxido ring furnish the novel 2,3 β -dihydroxy-(23 \rightarrow 10) oxido-5,10-friedooleana-9(11),12-dien-28-oic acid (mimusopsic acid) **17**. The acids **16** and **17** represent the first members of a hitherto unknown 5,10-friedooleanane (mimusopane) skeleton **19**.

The other new triterpenes isolated from the acid hydrolysate of the MeOH extract of the plant are mimusopgenone **20** and mimugenone³² **21**.

Saponins containing protobassic acid as the aglycone have been isolated from a number of plants³³⁻³⁵. Considerable attention is being given in recent years for evaluation of antitumor activity of triterpene acids and encouraging results in this regard have been published³⁶⁻³⁸. The

triterpene acids 14 and 15 with new skeleton which are derivable from protobassic acid containing saponins, are of much interest to study their structure-activity relationship.

Acaciasides A and B

In continuation of our chemical investigation on the pharmaceutically important naturally occurring saponins³⁹⁻⁴⁸, we isolated two acylated triterpenoid bisglycosides acaciasides A 22 and B 23 from the water-soluble saponin fraction obtained from the pericarps of *Acacia auriculiformis* A. Cunn. (Leguminosae)⁴⁹. This plant species which produces large amounts of fruits is abundantly available throughout India. The saponins which are present as a complex mixture are the main constituents of the pericarps of the plants. The water-soluble saponin fraction from the fruits exhibited strong spermicidal property⁵⁰ as well as antifilarial activity⁵¹. The structural features of the two complex saponins 22 and 23 were elucidated by a combination of fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectroscopy, and strategic chemical degradations⁴⁹. These useful biological properties of the saponins as well as their easy availability from a widely occurring plant source made them the ideal target for large-scale isolation and beneficial exploitation.

The saponins occurring widely in nature possess a broad spectrum of biological properties⁵²⁻⁵⁸. Although the saponins are highly toxic when given intravenously to higher animals, their toxic effects are very much lower when they are administered orally⁵⁹. Many of the most common saponins of foods and feeding-stuffs are apparently without

significant oral toxicity. However, saponins from non-edible plants are known to be highly toxic to man and other species. Ginseng, the widely known plant drug, has been used for centuries as an expensive traditional medicine and the ginseng saponins have been the subject of much discussion⁶⁰⁻⁶³. Saikosaponins from *Bupleurum* species (Umbelliferae) have been reported to have antiviral⁶⁴, anti-inflammatory⁶⁵, and plasma-cholesterol lowering⁶⁶ activities. The saponins from *Gymnema sylvestree*, a reputed Indian medicinal plant, have attracted much attention in recent years for their varied biological activities⁶⁷. Although the saponins often occur as complex mixtures, it is possible sometimes to isolate individual major saponins by simplified nonchromatographic methods. For example, a simplified method for isolation of asiaticoside, a potential antileprotic agent⁶⁸ and whose complete structure has been determined by single crystal X-ray analysis⁶⁹, has been patented⁷⁰.

Acid-catalyzed rearrangement of aglycones

The saponins are composed of aglycone and sugar moieties which are recovered after hydrolysis and separately investigated for structure elucidation. Acid hydrolysis is often used; however, if a saponin contains an acid-labile aglycone, artefacts are obtained. Arjunglucoside-1⁷¹ 24 on alkaline hydrolysis yielded arjungenin 25. Acid hydrolysis of the glucoside, however, generated a major aglycone which

was characterized as tomentosic acid **26** by spectroscopic and *X*-ray analysis⁷². The acid **26** was isolated by Row and Rao⁷³ from *Terminalia tomentosa* not as a saponin but as a naturally occurring triterpene. In our attempt to elucidate the mechanism of transformation of arjungenin **25** to tomentosic acid **26** it was observed that although arjungenin **25** on being boiled with 5% methanolic hydrochloric acid produced tomentosic acid **26**, the methyl ester of arjungenin was recovered unchanged after similar acid treatment. Consequently, the epimerization of 19 α -OH was reasonably thought to be via lactonization. Isolation of the intermediate lactone²⁷ strongly supported this presumption and mechanism of the transformation was rationalized⁷². Aoki and Suga⁷⁴ reported acid-catalyzed epimerization of the 16 β -OH group of cochalic acid. They ascribed this phenomenon to thermodynamic stability. However, longispinogenin glycoside which contains a 28-CH₂OH instead of a 28-COOH⁴⁰ yielded, on acid hydrolysis, the genuine aglycone longispinogenin instead of its 16-epimer, primulagenin A. This experiment demonstrated that epimerization of the 16 β -OH group to 16 α -OH does not take place on prolonged treatment with acid if there is no 28-COOH group available to form the 28 \rightarrow 16 lactone. Inspection of Dreiding models also suggested that the 16 α -OH (axial) group is not thermodynamically more stable than the 16 β -OH (equatorial) group. As such this epimerization was also suggested to occur via lactonization between 28-COOH and 16 β -OH. Thus in both cases, the kinetically controlled products are formed and it was suggested that where the lactonization and delactonization are possible in a triterpene the kinetically controlled product is obtained exclusively⁷².

During isolation of saponins by acid hydrolysis of the saponins from *Medicago hispida*⁴⁵, it was observed that soyasapogenol B **28** which is a genuine aglycone is converted to soyasapogenol D **29** and soyasapogenol F **30** Jurzysta⁷⁵ and Price *et al*⁷⁶ reported that compounds **29** and **30** are artefacts of compound **28**. However, the mechanism of formation of these products which apparently seemed to be rather unusual had been rationalized. We observed⁴⁰ that longispinogenin or its glycosides cochorusins A and D₂ containing 16 β -hydroxy group did not yield any $\Delta^{13(18)}$ -aglycone on similar treatment with aqueous methanolic hydrochloric acid. It was, therefore, indicated that the 22 β (axial)-hydroxy group present in soyasapogenol B **28** or its glycosides might have some role in inducing this transformation. Assuming all-chair conformation of **28** having D/E *cis*-fusion, inspection of its Dreiding model disclosed that the 22 β -axial hydroxyl experiences strong steric interaction with the 20 β -axial methyl, in addition to that with the 17-methyl group. Migration of the double bond from the 12 : 13 to 13 : 18 position transforms the 22 β -

hydroxyl from axial to equatorial orientation, thereby relaxing the 1,3-diaxial interaction. Substitution of the 22-hydroxy group in **30** with a methoxy group may then occur via (a) its protonation, (b) elimination of the protonated group through participation of the 13 : 18 double bond which is favourably disposed to form a protonated cyclopropane as intermediate and (c) attack by a molecule of methanol on the intermediate carbocation, to generate a methoxy derivative with retention of configuration⁴⁵.

Macrocyclic spermidine alkaloids

Macrocyclic spermidine and spermine alkaloids which belong to the class of polyamine conjugates are comparatively a new group of plant bases. These are formed by a polyamine (spermidine or spermine) and a properly functionalized aliphatic or cinnamoylic acid or one of their derivatives. The free bases putrescine, spermidine and spermine are believed to play important roles in cellular differentiation and proliferation⁷⁷. The polyamine levels in dividing cells, e.g. cancer cells are much higher than the resting cells⁷⁸ and this phenomenon has been exploited in chemotherapy and diagnostic test for malignant tumors^{79,80}. Since early 1970s many unique polyamine conjugates have been isolated which possess diverse biochemical profiles⁸¹.

We isolated three spermidine alkaloids designated caesalpinine A **31**, B **32**^{82,83} and C **33**⁸⁴ from the leaves of *Caesalpinia digyna* Rottl. (Leguminosae). The plant is a prickly scandent shrub growing in eastern India, Burma, and Ceylon. It is reputed for its use in phthisis, scrofula, and diabetes⁸⁵. Caesalpinine B **32** and C **33** were found to be identical with celacinnine and celalocinnine isolated from *Maytenus arbutifolia* (Celastraceae)⁸⁶. Caesalpinine A **31** turned out to be a novel macrocyclic spermidine alkaloid with a new skeleton. The structure and stereochemistry of the alkaloid were determined by mass, nmr and single crystal *X*-ray analysis. It possesses a 13-membered lactam ring fused to a five-membered lactam ring. It also contains two monosubstituted benzene rings. The *X*-ray investigations of **31** demonstrated the presence of two independent molecules linked by a hydrogen bond in the asymmetric

unit. In spermidine alkaloids the formation of a 13-membered lactam ring is a normal phenomenon. However, the unique structural feature of caesalpinine A **31** is its 5-membered lactam ring formed by an interesting biogenetic pathway.

A proposition for the biosynthesis of caesalpinine A **31** envisages participation of two cinnamic acid moieties and a dehydrospermidine. Periphylline, a dehydrospermidine moiety containing alkaloid has, in fact, been isolated from a plant source⁸⁷. The C–C bond is believed to arise via protonation of the dehydrospermidine as proposed in Scheme 4, and subsequent attack by the cinnamoyl bond with concomitant hydroxylation.

Scheme 4

Another proposition envisages involvement of one molecule of cinnamic acid, a molecule each of benzoylactic acid and an appropriately substituted spermidine rather than spermidine itself. Elimination of the spermidine substituent (possibly involving the aziridinium ion) is followed by an attack from the carbanion derived from benzoylactic acid with the formation of a new C–C bond. The other reactions involved in the biogenesis are of well-established nature, viz. Michael addition, carbonyl reduction and amide formation. The carbonyl reduction step (and possibly even the cyclization to the γ -lactam) necessarily follows the C–C bond formation and the generation of the other C–N bonds may either precede or succeed the above step.

Perspectives

The advances in extraction technology, separation science, and analytical and spectroscopic techniques have greatly increased the prospect of discovery of complex natural products of novel carbon frameworks possessing useful biochemical profiles. Natural products are also expected to play a significant role in agriculture as pesticides and herbicides. Insect, pest or weed control by using synthetic chemicals results in toxic residues in soil and plants. The crops contaminated with such residues are health-hazard and as such natural plant chemicals will undoubtedly play a greater role in the future of pest control. A number of chemical companies are evaluating plant extracts and chemicals for the commercial use in agriculture. The com-

plex structures of many plant chemicals preclude their economical chemical synthesis. However, genetically engineered synthetic technique has the potential to solve this problem. In fact, the feasibility of multi-enzyme, one-flask total synthesis of natural products has already been demonstrated by the preparation of a tetramethyl corphinoid structure and of the alkaloid strictosidine by gene transfer and overexpression of the corresponding gene products in *E. coli*⁸⁸. Continued attempts to synthesize complex natural products by the application of this technology are anticipated.

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